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Recycled Aggregates Effect on Concrete Mechanical Performance Subjected to High Temperatures

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Synopsis: This study presents the results of an experimental campaign aimed at investigating the influence of recycled aggregates, derived from concrete debris (i.e., recycled concrete aggregates, RCAs), on the mechanical performance of the resulting concrete (i.e., Recycled Aggregate Concrete, RAC) after the exposure at elevated temperatures. As a matter of principle, RCAs are, generally, more porous in comparison with natural aggregates, due to the presence of the Attached Mortar (AM) and, this, may affect the physical properties of the aggregates as well as the RAC performance produced with RCAs. For this reason, in order to promote the possible use of RCAs for structural concrete production there is a strong need of understanding the influence of RCAs on the concrete performance, especially when these mixtures are subjected under “extreme conditions”. In this aim, the present experimental campaign investigates the “residual” mechanical performance of both ordinary and high strength concrete class (i.e., C25 and C65) produced with coarse RCAs (up to 100 %) and subjected at elevated temperatures (up to 650°C). The results unveil the role of the AM on affecting the compressive and tensile strengths as well as the elastic modulus of RACs exposed to elevated temperatures.

Keywords: high temperatures, mechanical behavior, recycled aggregate concrete, recycled concrete aggregate, residual strength

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays concrete is certainly the most widely used material in the construction sector for both structural and non-structural applications [1] and, the aggregates, generally, represent between 70-80% (in volume) of the concrete mixtures, significantly contributing to the development of the resulting mechanical performance of the composite [2]. As a matter of the fact, the aggregates are employed in concrete both for economic reasons, since they are cheaper than cement, as well as for their engineering characteristics (e.g., thermal stability) [3].

Moreover, since sustainability is becoming a fundamental requirement also for the concrete industry, in the last decades, extensive research has been carried on the viability of using Recycled Concrete Aggregates (RCAs), i.e., recycled aggregates derived from end-of-life concrete members debris, or other alternative aggregates [4][5][6][7], for the production of new structural concrete mixtures leading to the so-called Recycled Aggregate Concretes (RACs) [8]. For these reasons, the main effects of incorporating RCAs on the resulting key mechanical performance and physical properties [9][10][11] of RACs are now reasonably well-known [12].

Nonetheless, there are still some issues that need to be addressed, among which the RACs' behavior when subjected to extreme conditions, namely when exposed to fire and/or to high temperatures.

As a matter of principle, the presence of the Attached Mortar (AM) in RCAs leads to have a higher amount of mortar within the resulting RACs and, consequently, a lower amount of natural rocks in the final composite. It is worth mentioning that up to 600 °C (1112 °F) most of the aggregates exhibit thermal expansion and, as a consequence, internal stresses give rise to cracks occurring mainly at the bonding interfaces [13]. At this stage, the mechanical performances of "ordinary" concrete mixtures are already highly compromised. Then, since the RCA is composed of two distinct elements (i.e., AM and "old" natural aggregates), the number and types of interfaces increases leading to a higher probability of concrete degradation after the exposure to high temperatures. For instance, *Laneyrie et al.* [14] subjected normal and high strength concrete produced with RCAs to heating and cooling cycles, followed by constant high temperature exposure. The authors observed that during the heating phase the recycled concrete presented less fragmentation, but, on the other hand, some of high strength concrete samples exhibited an explosive fragmentation. On the other hand, *Dong et al.* [15] compared the fire resistance performance of columns of conventional concrete with that of concrete made with coarse RCAs (replacement rate of 100%). The results showed that the resistance of RAC columns is better than ordinary concrete columns, characterized by the same compressive strength and, in addition, they observed that the rate of heat transfer from the surface to the interior of the column increases with the increase of the concrete's compressive strength for both RAC and ordinary concrete columns. In a further study, *Zega and Di Maio* [16] performed recycled concretes with water-to-cement ratios of 0.40 and 0.70, and made with three different types of natural coarse aggregate (siliceous gravel and quartzitic crushed stone) were exposed to 500 °C (932 °F) for 1 h. In these experiments, the Authors confirmed the better post-fire mechanical performance of recycled concretes, particularly for the lowest w/c (i.e., 0.40) and when produced with quartzitic aggregates. *Vieira et al.* [13] evaluated the residual compressive strength of recycled concretes with different replacement rates (i.e., 0%, 20%, 50% and 100%) after being subjected to high temperatures for a period of 1 h to temperatures of 400 °C (752 °F), 600 °C (1112 °F) and 800 °C (1472 °F): according to their results, the Authors concluded that the post-fire performance of recycled concrete, in general, was similar to conventional concrete.

In this context, the present study was developed in order to investigate the residual mechanical performance of concrete made with recycled concrete coarse aggregates after exposure to high temperatures, up to 650°C (1202 °F). Specifically, this research focuses on the residual mechanical properties of normal and high-strength RCAs for a coarse aggregate replacement ratio equal to 100%.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Materials

For the production of the concrete mixtures, quartz sand, characterized by a nominal diameter smaller than 4.75 mm (No. 4), was used as natural fine aggregate while natural (i.e., a granite type stone) and recycled concrete aggregates were used as the coarse fraction, characterized by a nominal diameter between 4.75 mm (No. 4) and 9.5 mm (3/8 in.) (see **Fig. 1**).

Several tests were performed on both natural and recycled aggregates and the results of their physical properties are reported in **Table 1**.

The specific gravity and the water absorption tests of natural coarse aggregate and RCA were performed according to the NBR NM 53 [17]. Meanwhile, the specific gravity and the water absorption capacity of natural fine aggregates were performed according to the NBR NM 52 [18] and NBR NM 30 [19], respectively.

As can be observed from **Table 1**, the specific gravity of RCAs is lower than the natural aggregate, while the water absorption of the natural aggregates is lower than the recycled ones, which may be due to the presence of the Attached Mortar that, consequently, increases the RCAs' porosity [8].

The Portland cement used in this research, labelled CPV – ARI according to the National Brazilian Standard (NBR) 5733 [20], was produced by Holcim.

Finally, a superplasticizer, characterized by a solid concentration content of 30% and a specific gravity of 1.087 g/cm³ (0.04 lb/in.³), was used within the mixes for workability control.

Mixture proportioning and specimen preparation

The mixture proportioning for the concretes analyzed herein was based on the Compressible Packing Model (CPM), proposed by *de Larrard* [21]. This model considers that all the grains interact within each other influencing the overall density of the mixture and, for this reason, the main physical and mechanical properties of concrete are governed by the overall packing density of the granular skeleton.

Based on the CPM, an optimization procedure was performed with the software *BetonLab Pro 3* [21] for designing the concrete mixtures composition. It is worth highlighting that the CPM assumes that during the mixing procedure, the aggregates should be employed in dry conditions and their water absorption capacity at 24 hours should be considered by introducing additional water for their saturation. However, the RCAs are, generally, characterized by a significantly higher water absorption capacity with respect to natural aggregates and, recent studies [8][9][22] demonstrated that they are not able to absorb such amount of water during the mixing time and, as a consequence, some extra water in the mixture could cause an increase in the effective water-cement ratio [9]. For this reason, in the present study some conditions were applied in accordance with the methodology proposed by *Amario et al.* [9]: the RCAs are employed in fully dried condition and a 50% of their water absorption capacity is considered for saturation during mixing. Two classes of compressive strength were considered: 25 MPa (3626 psi) and 65 MPa (9427 psi) at 28 days. These mixtures are labeled “C25” and “C65”, respectively. Then, for each strength class, two mixtures were produced: a reference concrete with only natural aggregates and a RAC mixtures with 100% of coarse RCAs replacement level (by volume). The complete concrete mixtures composition is reported in **Table 2**.

The replacement level of RCA 0 and 100% were labeled “00” and “100”, respectively. Thus, for instance, C65-00 represents a mixture with estimated compressive strength of 65 MPa (9427 psi) and with 0% of RCA content relative to the total coarse aggregate volume. All the concrete mixtures were designed for a slump value ranging between 120 and 140 mm.

For each mixture, several samples were prepared for the mechanical characterization (i.e., compressive strength, elastic modulus and tensile splitting strength): concrete cylinders (h=150 mm (5.90 in.) and d=75mm (2.95 in.)) of the same mix were cast from the same batch to ensure uniformity. The procedure for preparing the concrete mixes was as follows: coarse aggregates and sand were mixed for 1 minute, then, 50% of total water was added and the materials were mixed for 1 minute; the cement was added and the materials were mixed for more 1 minute; and, finally, the other half of the water and the superplasticizer were added and the mixing operation was continued for 8 minutes added.

Experimental methods

Specimens from all types of concrete, besides being tested at ambient temperature, about 22 °C (71.6 °F), were subjected to the following three temperatures for a period of 1 h: 150 °C (302 °F), 400 °C (752 °F) and 650 °C (1202 °F). At 28 days, the specimens were heated in furnace at 60 °C (140 °F) ± 1 °C (33.8 °F) until reaching mass constancy to prevent spalling due to excessive moisture emission during the heating process. Subsequently, the specimens were heated in the electric furnace Elektro Therm (**Fig. 2**) with a constant rate of 2°C/min (35.6 °F/min) until the target temperature is reached (**Fig. 3**).

After the soaking for a period of 1 h, the specimens were left cooling within the furnace, with close door, until temperature decreased at ambient temperature. After that, the specimens were moved to the laboratory for the mechanical characterization.

In order to evaluate the post-fire residual mechanical properties of concrete, the following tests were carried out in specimens cooled at ambient temperature: compressive strength and elastic modulus, four cylindrical specimens with 75 mm (2.95 in.) of diameter and 150 mm (5.90 in.) of height for each temperature, according to NBR 5739 [23], elastic modulus, according to NBR 8522 [24], and tensile splitting strength, four cylindrical specimens with 75 mm (2.95 in.) of diameter and 75 mm (2.95 in.) of height for each temperature, according to NBR 7222 [25]. The specimens were tested at a rate of axial displacement of 0.1 mm/min (0.04 in./min) for the compressive tests and 0.3 mm/min (0.12 in./min) for the tensile splitting ones.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

An overview of the experimental results in terms of residual compressive strength, residual Elastic modulus and residual spitting strength, after the exposure at elevated temperatures at 28 days of curing, for both C25 and C65 mixtures, is reported in **Table 3**.

From the experimental data reported in **Table 3** it emerges that, as also expected, the mechanical performances are highly reduced after the exposure to elevated temperatures and this is more evident in the case of 400 °C (752 °F) and 650 °C (1202 °F). A more comprehensive analysis of the results is proposed in the following subsections.

Compressive strength

Fig. 4 shows the average compressive strength for C25 (yellow bars) and C65 (blue bars) mixtures after the exposure at high temperatures.

First of all, for the normal-strength class (i.e., C25) the average results reported in **Fig. 4** indicate that for both ordinary (i.e., C25-00) and RAC (i.e., C25-100) mixtures a similar trend occurred. Specifically, after being subjected to 150 °C (302 °F), the reference (i.e., C25-00) and the RAC mixtures showed a residual compressive strength higher than in the cases obtained at room temperature, and, moreover the concrete C25-100 presented a higher increase of the resistance in comparison with the mixture C25-00. However, after 400 °C (752 °F) the C25 mixtures showed a decrease of strength, and, also in this case, the concrete produced with 100% of recycled aggregates showed a higher reduction than the reference one. This behavior was repeated after exposure at 650 °C, in which the reduction rate of C25-100 was again higher than C25-00.

Quantitatively, there was an increase in the residual compressive strength value of around 11% for the mixtures C25-00 and around 17% for C25-100 when exposed to 150 °C (302 °F). Then, when the heating reached 400 °C (752 °F), the reduction of the compressive strength values for the reference mixture was equal to 9%, whereas for the mixture produced with only coarse RCAs the reduction was around 10%. In addition, after the exposure to 650 °C (1202 °F) the compressive strength of C25-00 and C25-100 suffered loss of approximately 44% and 49%, respectively. The loss of resistance can be associated to the dehydration of the hydrated calcium silicate (CSH) gel, especially after heating at 650 °C (1202 °F), since, generally, at 500 °C (932°F) 70% of the CSH dehydration reaction occurs, becoming even more critical after 600 °C (1112 °F) [26][27]. Moreover, the pressure caused by the water vapor in the internal pores, and the transformations of the aggregates, caused close to 400 °C (752 °F), also contributed to the observed behavior.

Through **Fig. 4** it is possible to observe also the variation of the compressive strength for high strength-class concretes (i.e., C65). From the figure it is highlighted a similar behavior registered for the normal-strength class (i.e., C25). Particularly, after being subjected to 150 °C (302 °F), the RAC mix (i.e., C65-100) present an increase in the compressive strength of around 3%, while in the case of C65-00 it increases of around 2%. Then, when the exposure temperature was equal to 400 °C (752 °F) the compressive strength decreased in both mixtures: the reference concrete (i.e., C65-00) showed a 4% reduction while the C65-100 exhibited reductions of around 10%, respectively. Finally, at 650 °C (1202 °F) the compressive strength suffered even greater reductions, however the mixtures presented similar reduction rates of around about 47% and 45% for the recycled mixtures and the reference one, respectively.

Elastic Modulus

The **Fig. 5** shows the variation of the residual Elastic Modulus with the temperature for normal and high strength concretes class.

From the figure it emerges that the exposure to high temperatures caused negative impacts also on the modulus of elasticity. As a matter of principle, it was affected by the exposure to elevated temperatures even more critically than the compressive strength. In fact, the exposure at 150 °C (302 °F) caused a small reduction of the elastic modulus for all the mixtures, where the presence of RCAs within the mixture, increases the reduction of E modulus, but, on the other hand at 400 °C (752 °F) and 650 °C (1202 °F) the presence of recycled aggregates did not significantly affect the response of concrete, with practically the same reduction rates for all mixtures. Specifically, it was registered a reduction on the residual E modulus value of around 2% for the mixtures C25-00 and around 11% for C25-100 when exposed to 150 °C (302 °F), meanwhile for the C65-00 and C65-100 a decrease of around 8% and 9% occurred, respectively. Then, after the exposure a 400 °C (752 °F), the reduction of the elastic modulus values for the C25 mixtures was equal to 43-44%, whereas for the C65 it was equal to 48% in the

case of C65-00 and reached a value of 54% in the case of C65-100. Finally, after the exposure to 650 °C (1202 °F) the compressive strength of C25-00 and C25-100 suffered loss of approximately 93% meanwhile lower decreasing ratio were observed for the high-strength class (i.e., around 82% for both reference and RAC mixtures).

Splitting Strength

The splitting strength values, obtained before and after heating process, for both normal and high strength concretes are reported in **Fig. 6**.

The results showed that the exposure to 150°C (302 °F), 400°C (752 °F) and 650 °C (1202 °F) caused reduction in the values of the tensile strength. For the normal-strength class C25, it is observed that as the temperature was increased the more critical were the drops in the values of this property and that the reduction rates presented between the several mixtures analyzed herein were, generally, similar. In quantitative terms, after exposure to 150 °C (302 °F), C25-00 showed a drop of around 9% while C25-100 had a reduction of 11%. At 400 °C (752 °F) the loss of tensile strength was in the order of 17% for the reference concrete and around 22% for the recycled concrete, meanwhile, at 650 °C (1202 °F), the reduction was similar for the two mixtures, close to 55%. Concretes of class C65-00 and C65-100 showed similar variations when submitted to 150 °C (302 °F), in the order of 10%. After exposure at 400 °C (752 °F), the recycled concrete showed a decrease of splitting strength more pronounced, while the conventional concrete had its resistance decreased by 12% and the recycled one presented around 23%, and after exposure at 650 °C (1202 °F), C65-100 presented inferior performance (i.e., splitting strength reduction of around 67%) in comparison with the reference C65-00 one where a decrease of around 50% was registered: this can be justified by the greater amount of mortar presents in the RAC due to the old Attached Mortar present in the recycled concrete aggregates [8].

CONCLUSIONS

This study analyzed the mechanical behavior of normal and high strength recycled aggregate concrete under elevated temperatures. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- the recycled aggregate concretes and the ordinary reference concrete mixtures exhibited similar mechanical performance when exposed to high temperatures. Therefore, based on the results obtained herein, no relationship seems to exist between the degradation of residual mechanical properties studied and the replacement rate of the RCA for the different exposure temperatures analyzed herein;
- elevated temperature has a significant effect on the compressive behavior of the concretes: after the exposure to 150°C (302 °F) its compressive strength was increase, while after exposure to 400 °C (752 °F) and 650 °C (1202 °F) the compressive strength decreases;
- the elastic modulus decreased quickly with the increase temperature. The deterioration of elastic modulus due to high temperatures is more severe that of residual strengths. As a matter of fact, the C25 mixtures showed an inferior behavior compare to C65 concretes in this property and the increase of RCA percentage in concrete has not influence on the elastic modulus;
- the tensile strength also decreased with an increase of the exposure temperature. The mixtures C25 presented similar behavior for the different replacement rates of the RCA. However, for class C65 the experimental results could not to indicate if the recycled aggregate has some influence about thermal response of the concretes, because to 150 °C (302 °F), C65-50 presented perform better than the other mixtures, at 400 °C (752 °F) all concretes exhibit similar performance and at 650 °C (1202 °F), C65-100 exhibited inferior residual tensile strength.

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TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 1–Physical properties for natural and recycled aggregates.

Aggregate type	Particle density	Water absorption capacity at 24h
	kg/m ³ (lb/ft ³)	%
<i>Natural sand</i>	2298.3 (143)	0.34
<i>Coarse NAT</i>	2711.4 (169)	1.81
<i>Coarse RCA</i>	2610.0 (163)	5.28

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Table 2–Mixtures composition

Mix	NAT kg (lbs)	RCA kg (lbs)	Sand kg (lbs)	Cement kg (lbs)	sp. kg (lbs)	W _{tot} kg (lbs)	W _{eff} kg (lbs)	w/c _{eff}
C25-00	941.9 (2077)	-	798.4 (1760)	300 (661)	4 (9)	216.9 (478)	200 (441)	0.66
C25-100	-	941.8 (2076)	829.3 (1828)	268.2 (591)	5.3 (12)	206.9 (456)	172.9 (381)	0.64
C65-00	895.2 (1974)	-	758.8 (1673)	500 (1102)	6.67 (15)	187.1 (412)	170 (375)	0.34
C65-100	-	858.4 (1892)	755.8 (1666)	550 (1213)	7.33 (16)	179.2 (395)	150 (331)	0.27

Table 3–Overview of the experimental results

Mix	Temperature °C (°F)	Compressive strength MPa (psi)	Elastic modulus GPa (psi)	Splitting strength MPa (psi)
C25-00	22 (71.6)	25.50 (3698)	20.10 (2915264)	2.30 (333)
	150 (302)	28.20 (4090)	19.70 (2857249)	2.10 (304)
	400 (752)	23.10 (3350)	7.50 (1087785)	1.90 (275)
	650 (1202)	14.20 (2060)	1.50 (217557)	1.10 (159)
C25-100	22 (71.6)	28.00 (4061)	21.40 (3103813)	2.70 (391)
	150 (302)	32.80 (4757)	19.00 (2755722)	2.40 (348)
	400 (752)	25.30 (3669)	7.60 (1102289)	2.10 (304)
	650 (1202)	14.40 (2089)	1.80 (261068)	1.20 (174)
C65-00	22 (71.6)	65.20 (9456)	30.70 (4452667)	4.10 (594)
	150 (302)	67.30 (9761)	28.10 (4075568)	3.70 (536)
	400 (752)	62.60 (9079)	16.00 (2320608)	3.60 (522)
	650 (1202)	36.10 (5236)	5.40 (783205)	2.10 (304)
C65-100	22 (71.6)	67.40 (9776)	30.70 (4452667)	3.90 (565)
	150 (302)	70.20 (10182)	28.00 (4061064)	3.50 (507)
	400 (752)	60.90 (8833)	14.20 (2059540)	3.00 (435)
	650 (1202)	35.50 (5149)	5.60 (812213)	1.30 (188)

Fig. 1–Natural and recycled aggregates: (a) natural sand; (b) coarse natural aggregates; (c) coarse RCAs

Fig. 2–Heating equipment details

Fig. 3–Heating and cooling rates

Fig. 4–Residual compressive strength results.

Fig. 5– Residual elastic modulus results

Fig. 6– Residual splitting strength results

